

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15846155

Prevalence Of Peer Pressure And Religious Affiliation On Adolescent Heterosexual Behaviours Among Senior Secondary School Students In Rivers State, Nigeria

Charitoo-Spiff, Inekiengha Mercy¹, Agbo, David Ito² & Agburuka, Chinonso Stella³

**School of Primary Education and Early Childhood Education,
Isaac Jasper Boro College of Education Sagbama, Bayelsa State¹,**

**Department of Educational Management,
Faculty of Educational Foundation, University of Calabar²**

**Department of Educational Psychology,
Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Port Harcourt³**

Email: charitoomercy@gmail.com¹ divadd42@gmail.com² chinsomoa56@yahoo.com³

ABSTRACT

The study investigates the prevalence of peer pressure and religious affiliation on adolescent 2 heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria. two (3) research questions and 2 hypotheses were answered and tested in the study, respectively. The descriptive cross-sectional research design was utilized. The population of the study consisted of all public senior secondary school students in the 2024/2025 academic year in Rivers State, with a total of one hundred and eighty-five thousand, two hundred and twenty-five (185,225) students. From the total population of 185,225 students, 400 sample size was generated using the Taro Yamane (1967) statistical formula. Thereafter, the sample size for the study was multiplied by three, representing the three senatorial districts. An adapted semi-structured closed ended questionnaire developed by the researcher was used for data collection. The data for this study were collected through the administration of a pre-designed, re-tested, semi-structured questionnaire to respondents. To ensure the validity of the research instrument (the questionnaire), there was an extensive literature review relating to the topic. Furthermore, to examine the evidence of the face and content validity, the instruments were validated by two experts. Split half method was used for the reliability of the instrument. The analysis revealed a reliability index of 0.94 for socio-demographic data, prevalence of heterosexual behavior was 0.78. The data was computed and analyzed using Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) version 23 and Microsoft Excel. Univariate (frequency and simple percentage) were used to analyze demographic variables, while descriptive and inferential (chi-square) statistical analysis was used to determine the relationship between the proxies of the independent variable. The findings of the study reveals that a significant number of adolescents possess knowledge about reproductive health, yet they still participate in risky sexual behaviors, including kissing and sexual intercourse. This phenomenon may be attributed to various influencing factors, such as peer pressure and the pervasive impact of religious affiliation. Consequently, it was recommended among others that religious/faith-based organizations should use their positions as a leverage to encourage adolescents to abstain from premarital sex.

Keywords: Peer pressure, religious affiliation, adolescent, heterosexual, behaviours, senior secondary schools, and Rivers State.

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) categorizes adolescents as individuals aged between 10 and 19 years. This age group's proportion varies between developed and developing nations (WHO, 2019). The transition phase from childhood to adulthood is referred to as adolescence. Nigeria possesses one of the largest youth populations, with one out of every four individuals being an adolescent aged 10–19 years (Nigeria Demographic Health Survey, 2018; World Population Review, 2015). This young demographic forms a significant and vital segment of Nigeria's overall population, yet they encounter numerous sexual and reproductive health challenges (United Nations Children's Fund, 2020). Brizio *et al.* (2015) describe an adolescent as a young male or female who has outgrown childhood but is not yet deemed an adult. Adolescence is typically understood as the timeframe that spans from the onset of puberty to full adulthood. There is no fixed timeline for adolescent development; each individual matures in their unique manner and at their own pace. The process of adolescent development is characteristically non-linear, marked by sudden growth spurts and fluctuating levels of maturity. In developed countries, adolescents comprise just 21 percent of the population, whereas in developing countries like Nigeria, they account for 29 percent. Recent data indicates that there are over 1.5 billion individuals aged 10-24 years, which is the highest figure recorded to date, and 85 percent of this group resides in developing nations (WHO 2019).

Adolescents have reached biological maturity and can reproduce; however, engaging in sexual activities during adolescence can lead to numerous long-term negative outcomes. Additionally, when adolescent girls partake in risky sexual behaviors, they are at a higher risk for reproductive health issues and may face teenage pregnancies, which can force them to make challenging choices between becoming teenage parents or terminating their pregnancies. This challenge arises because adolescent girls often struggle to communicate openly about sexuality, leading them to acquire information primarily from boys. Moreover, engaging in risky sexual behaviors can also increase the likelihood of adolescents contracting sexually transmitted infections, including human immunodeficiency virus/acquired immune deficiency syndrome (HIV/AIDS). Furthermore, if adolescents delay seeking treatment for sexually transmitted infections, they may experience long-term health complications. In addition to health issues, adolescent sexual activity can negatively affect academic performance; a perspective supported by Lanari *et al.* (2020), who found that sexual involvement correlates with reduced participation in educational activities. According to the Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS) (2019), 80% of HIV infections among adolescents in sub-Saharan Africa occur in girls aged 15-19 years. Adolescent girls and young women are also twice as likely to be living with HIV compared to their male counterparts of the same age, despite reporting having only one sexual partner and fewer sexual encounters. This situation has led researchers in various parts of the world to focus more on adolescents' reproductive health in order to develop lasting solutions to some deviant social and health behaviors that deeply affect society (United Nations Children Fund, 2020).

In Nigeria, traditional norms significantly influence sexual behaviors, much like in many other countries. This may explain why, several decades ago, a girl's virginity until marriage was celebrated, and various taboos were established around premarital sexual activities. However, this trend is slowly changing, and there is a high prevalence of adolescents and young people engaging in sexual intercourse, which could pose challenges (Anoke-Ogbonna, 2013). Such behaviors are particularly common among Nigerian students, especially those in senior secondary schools and higher education institutions (Anoke-Ogbonna, 2013). This trend may be attributed to the decline of several customs and practices, as well as factors related to rapid urbanization and other influences such as family background, age, peer pressure, media impact, economic conditions, gender, and educational levels.

Forms of Adolescent Heterosexual Behaviour

Sexual behavior encompasses more than just sexual intercourse; it also includes actions like holding hands, kissing, and fondling. From the early stages of holding hands to casual hookups, heterosexual youth invest significant time thinking about, discussing, and engaging in romantic relationships. The quality of these adolescent relationships can have long-lasting effects on self-esteem and shape personal values regarding romance, intimate relationships, and sexuality (Mapalad & Psych, 2014). Research indicates that about one in three 13-year-olds has entered a romantic relationship, with this number increasing with age. By the age of 17, most youth have had some experience with romantic relationships, typically involving more than one; on average, adolescents experience around four such

relationships during their teenage years. However, cultural factors influence both the timing and number of these relationships. For example, Asian American teens tend to enter romantic relationships later than their peers, as dating during adolescence is often less accepted in Asian cultures.

Sexual minority youth face unique challenges in finding potential partners. While many adolescents meet romantic partners in school, sexual minority youth may struggle to establish these social connections due to discrimination and the relatively small number of peers who have come out. Perceived social norms also play a role in the quality of relationships. For instance, boys may adopt aggressive behaviors in romantic relationships if they believe aggression is typical among their peers. Similarly, having sexually experienced or older friends can increase the likelihood that a youth will become sexually active, as their sexual decision-making may be influenced by their expectations of peer approval or disapproval. To minimize the risks associated with adolescent romantic relationships, it is important to help young people develop skills that support healthy connections. Sexually active youth in positive relationships are more likely to engage in behaviors that reduce their risk of unintended pregnancies and sexually transmitted diseases (STDs), such as more consistent contraceptive use, greater openness about sexual histories, and increased sexual exclusivity (Weitzman et al., 2019). Furthermore, school and community-based programs designed to help youth recognize gender-based stereotypes, improve conflict management and communication skills, and reduce the acceptance of partner violence have proven effective in decreasing dating violence in adolescent relationships (Foshee et al., 2011).

Peer Pressure

According to Hardcastle (2012), a peer can be anyone you look up to in terms of behavior or someone who is considered to be your equal in age or ability. Peer pressure is defined as the act of persuading or encouraging someone to engage in certain behaviors. This can occur in two forms: direct and indirect. However, indirect peer pressure is often less noticeable than direct peer pressure. Williams and Anthony (2015) differentiate between peer influence, which refers to indirect forms of persuasion, and peer pressure, which pertains only to direct forms of persuasion, encouragement, or coercion to engage in specific behaviors.

The social influence of others is a continuous process that plays a significant role in an individual's socialization throughout their life. One of the most critical periods characterized by rapid changes is adolescence. During this time, peer influence is connected to a mutual influence process known as peer contagion, where peers become increasingly similar over time in various characteristics (Donlan et al., 2015). Peer relationships are significant determinants of adolescent heterosexual behavior. The quality of romantic relationships often reflects the quality of friendships: adolescents who have close and trusting friendships are likely to develop similar romantic relationships, while those who experience hostility and aggression in friendships may carry these tendencies into their romantic lives. Furthermore, the relational skills that youth develop in friendships—such as expressing differing viewpoints and resolving conflicts—are mirrored in their romantic relationships. According to Forman-Alberti (2015), peer relationships can promote risky sexual behaviors, as peers provide emotional support among teenagers. Peers exert influence in multiple ways; peer pressure can manifest directly—through explicit attempts by peers to encourage or discourage behaviors—or subtly, as when peers avoid or ostracize individuals who do not conform to group norms. As members of peer groups, adolescents encounter many subtle forms of social influence, such as peer expectations. In contrast, peer pressure refers to situations in which an adolescent consciously alters their behavior based on past experiences or peer reactions to avoid being laughed at, teased, or ostracized.

Wang et al. (2012) suggest that peer pressure is commonly associated with episodes of adolescent risk-taking behaviors, such as delinquency, drug abuse, and risky sexual activities. On the other hand, Halpern-Flesher et al. (2014) highlight that peer pressure can have a positive impact by encouraging adolescents to use contraceptive measures and practice safe sex to protect against sexually transmitted infections (STIs).

Religion Affiliation

The importance of religion in understanding the behavior of individuals, groups, and communities cannot be overstated. Numerous studies indicate that religiosity significantly influences adolescent behavior (Holmes et al., 2019; James & Ward, 2019; Somefun, 2019; Salas-Wright et al., 2017). According to Rumun (2014), religion is one of the most crucial social institutions, having widespread

effects on various aspects of people's lives, attitudes, and behaviors. This is because religion plays a vital role in the lives of individuals in every society, and its function as a moral framework is well acknowledged. Furthermore, religion serves an essential role in socialization by instilling the norms and values of society in children, thereby reinforcing societal values and moral beliefs. It provides guidance on what is considered right and wrong. In addition to offering moral support for societal norms, religion often includes the threat of supernatural sanctions, which adds a powerful directive for human behavior. By defining certain behaviors as sinful and others as "pleasing to God," there is strong pressure on believers to avoid the "sinful" actions and to adhere to the approved behaviors. Calatrava et al. (2021) assert that religiosity has a complex relationship with behavior, particularly with sexual behavior. Religion significantly influences youth behavior, making it a critical factor in discussions about youth sexuality in sub-Saharan Africa. Similarly, Verona (2011) suggests that religion is becoming an increasingly important aspect of the lives of many adolescents and young adults in Brazil. It provides them with opportunities to nurture close relationships and actively participate in a religious environment. Some religions promote clearer guidelines and objectives, along with punitive consequences, regarding various aspects of their younger followers' lives, including their sexual behavior. The influence of religion is often seen as a restrictive force, contributing to the postponement, reduction, or even restriction of certain behaviors, such as premarital sexual activity among adolescents. Additionally, the high value placed on marriage, especially by certain religious denominations in Brazil, such as Catholicism (particularly those churches impacted by the charismatic movement) and Pentecostal Protestantism, leads to the establishment of doctrines against premarital and extramarital sex. These religions also teach mechanisms for resisting these temptations. Violating religious norms may result in psychological consequences, such as feelings of guilt, public embarrassment, or the expectation of divine punishment.

Olaoye and Agbede (2022) investigated the prevalence and personal predictors of risky sexual behavior among in-school adolescents in the Ikenne Local Government Area of Ogun State, Nigeria. The study employed a descriptive cross-sectional design and utilized a multi-stage sampling technique to select 716 participants. Data was collected using a validated semi-structured questionnaire, which achieved a Cronbach's alpha score of 0.78. Frequency and logistic regression analyses were conducted to provide statistical responses to the research questions and hypotheses. The mean age of the participants was 15.2 ± 1.4 years, with 57.3% of the respondents being female. Over a quarter (35.5%) of the respondents were in senior secondary one (SS1) in high school. More than half (53.1%) had a good level of knowledge about risky sexual behavior, while 54% had a fair perception of it. The respondents exhibited moderately high attitudes toward risky sexual behavior (61.2%) and moderately high self-esteem (63.7%). The prevalence of risky sexual behavior among the respondents was 19.2%. The personal predictors identified for risky sexual behavior included age (odds ratio [OR] = 3.21; $p < 0.05$), gender (OR = 1.86; confidence interval [CI]: 1.26–2.69; $p < 0.05$), perception (OR = 2.58; CI: 1.55–4.30; $p < 0.05$), attitude (OR = 4.58; CI: 1.61–13.05; $p < 0.05$), and self-esteem (OR = 7.39; $p < 0.05$). In conclusion, the study found that the respondents' risky sexual behaviors are influenced by age, gender, attitude, perception, and self-esteem. It is recommended that educational materials addressing the negative effects of risky sexual behaviors be incorporated into the secondary school curriculum.

Darfour-Oduro et al. (2022) explored the impact of the social environment on the sexual behavior of adolescent girls across 12 sub-Saharan African countries in a cross-sectional study. The total analytic sample consisted of 22,067 adolescent girls. Descriptive statistics were generated to identify the characteristics of these girls, and independent samples t-tests were performed to assess the differences between social environment factors, age of sexual debut, and number of sexual partners. Logistic regression models were utilized to determine the association between the social environment and sexual debut. The results showed variability across the 12 countries. Almost one in five (19.9%) adolescent girls reported having engaged in sexual intercourse. The mean age of sexual debut was 13.21 years (with a range of 13.04–13.37 years), and the mean number of sexual partners was 2.19 (range: 2.08–2.29). The study found that adolescent girls who reported a lack of connection with their parents were more likely to debut sexual activity (adjusted odds ratio [aOR] = 1.32, 95% CI: 1.14–1.53, $p < 0.000$). Parental monitoring was significantly associated with sexual debut; however, after controlling for confounding variables (such as age, class grade, and drug use), the association was no

longer significant. Additionally, adolescent girls who felt supported by their peers had a significantly higher number of sexual partners compared to those who did not feel supported.

Chigbu et al. (2022) examined the relationship between parenting style and the sexual behavior of in-school adolescents in the South East Zone of Nigeria. The study assessed a population of 137,095 in-school adolescents in public senior secondary schools, from which a sample of 1,200 was drawn. Three research questions and one hypothesis were formulated for the study, which adopted a correlational survey design. Two instruments were used for data collection: the Parenting Style Questionnaire (PSQ), which had a reliability coefficient of 0.66, and the Sexual Behavior Questionnaire (SBQ), with a reliability coefficient of 0.78. The research questions were answered using mean, standard deviation, and simple regression analysis, while t-tests and multiple regression analyses were utilized to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The results indicated that in-school adolescents were exposed to authoritative, authoritarian, and permissive parenting styles. Their sexual behaviors included attraction to the opposite sex and engaging in sexual intercourse under the influence of alcohol, among others. The study found a direct positive relationship between parenting styles and the sexual behavior of adolescents; however, a weak variation in sexual behavior attributed to parenting style was noted. The findings suggested that parenting style has no significant relationship with the sexual behavior of in-school adolescents.

Statement of the Problem

Adolescents are anticipated to adhere to values such as abstaining from sexual activity until marriage, minimizing late-night outings, and following their parents' advice in order to avoid the dangers linked to unhealthy sexual conduct. Nonetheless, a significant number of adolescents engage in sexual activities, with the National Agency for the Control of AIDS (NACA) indicating that approximately 1.9 million adults and 130,000 children under 15 are living with HIV/AIDS in Nigeria. This circumstance underscores the need for focused initiatives for young people, as many instances of HIV transmission occur during the teenage years, with the virus potentially incubating for as long as 10 years.

In Rivers State, Nigeria, there is an increase in unintended pregnancies and sexually transmitted infections (STIs) among young people, underscoring a deficiency in knowledge, protective measures, and suitable guidance. The prevalence of early sexual initiation and high-risk behaviors is exacerbated by restricted access to comprehensive sexual education and socio-cultural obstacles that hinder open discussions regarding sexual health. A lack of sufficient government initiatives and prevailing cultural standards may further exacerbate these challenges, leading many young girls to quit school due to pregnancies and others being impacted by HIV/AIDS. Despite evidence of rising risky sexual behaviors among adolescents in Rivers State, there exists a scarcity of empirical studies on this issue in sub-Saharan Africa, with most existing research primarily concentrating on the western region of Nigeria. Therefore, the researcher intends to explore the prevalence of peer pressure and religious affiliation on influencing heterosexual behavior among students in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to investigate the prevalence of peer pressure and religious affiliation on adolescent heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine the influence of peer pressure on heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State.
2. assess the influence of religious affiliation on heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does peer pressure influence heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does religious affiliation influence heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses which were tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study.

1. There is no significant relationship between peer pressure and heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant relationship between religious affiliation and heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The descriptive cross-sectional research design was utilized to achieve the purpose of this study. The population of the study consisted of all public senior secondary school students in the 2024/2025 academic year in Rivers State with a total of one hundred and eighty-five thousand, two hundred and twenty-five (185,225) students. From the total population of 185,225 students, 400 sample size was generated using the Taro Yamane (1967) statistical formula. One thousand two hundred (1200) students were randomly selected from twelve (12) LGAs across the three (3) Senatorial Districts. For the composition of respondents, a non-proportionate stratified random sampling technique was utilized to sample equal (100) respondents from each of the sampled schools, thereby arriving at 1200 respondents which was used for the study. An adapted semi-structured closed-ended questionnaire developed by the researcher was used for data collection. The data for this study were collected through the administration of a pre-designed, re-tested, semi-structured questionnaire to respondents. To ensure the validity of the research instrument (the questionnaire), there was an extensive literature review relating to the topic. Furthermore, to examine the evidence of the face and content validity, the instruments were validated by two experts. Split half method was used for the reliability of the instrument. Fifty (50) copies of the questionnaire were administered on 50 students at the same time. Later, the questionnaires were numbered from 1 to 50. The even numbers were made to be group one (1) while odd numbers were made to be group two (2). Thereafter, the two groups of data were analyzed using Kuder Richardson version 20 (Dichotomous options). The analysis revealed a reliability index of 0.91 for socio-demographic data, prevalence of heterosexual behavior was 0.79. The researcher employed three research assistants to assist in administering the questionnaires to the students in the selected schools. The items on the instrument were read out to them, and the respondents followed the instructions in completing the questionnaire. The data collection exercise lasted for four (4) months. The data analysis method for the study was basically descriptive statistical analyses. The data was computed and analyzed using Statistical Product and Service Solutions (SPSS) version 23 and Microsoft Excel, descriptive and inferential (chi-square) statistical analysis was used to determine the relationship between the proxies of the independent variable (peer pressure and religious affiliation) on the dependent variable (adolescent heterosexual behaviour).

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *To what extent does peer pressure influences adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Peer Pressure as a determinant of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours

S.N		Frequency	Percent
1	My friends encourage me to have romantic relationships		
	No	192	16.0
	yes	1008	84.0
2	I accompany my friends to parties, music clubs		
	No	288	24.0
	Yes	912	76.0
3	My friends actively encourage me to have friends of opposite sex		
	No	288	24.0
	Yes	912	76.0
4	I watch romantic movies and pornography in company of my friends		
	No	288	24.0
	Yes	912	76.0
5	ve engaged in sexual activities because I was encouraged by my friends		
	No	384	32.0
	Yes	816	68.0
6	ve drunk alcohol in company of my friends		
		576	48.0
		624	52.0
	Average		
	No		368
	Yes		832

Source: Field survey (2023): Key: 0-25% = Low; 26-50% = Moderate; 51-100% = High

Table 1 show the frequency and percentage distribution of peer pressure as a determinant of adolescent heterosexual behaviour among senior secondary school students in Rivers State. According to the findings 84% reported having been encouraged by peers to engage in romantic relationships. Those who reported having been encouraged by friends to attend parties and music clubs have friends of the opposite sex and watch romantic movies and pornography by peers were 76%; while those who were encouraged by peers to engage in sexual activities were 68%. Adolescents who reported encouraged by peers to drink alcohol in order to have courage were 52%.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does religion affiliation influences adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Religious affiliation as a determinant of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours

S.N		Frequency	Percent
1	I engage regularly in religious activities		
	No	528	44.0
	Yes	672	56.0
2	My religion teaches against premarital sex		
	No	528	44.0
	Yes	672	56.0
3	Premarital sex is a sin before God		
	No	408	34.0
	Yes	792	66.0
4	I feel bad whenever I engage in sexual activities		
	No	864	72.0
	Yes	336	28.0
5	Having a boyfriend/ girlfriend is normal for me		
	No	1080	90.0
	Yes	120	10.0
	<i>Average</i>		
	<i>No</i>	682	56.8
	<i>Yes</i>	518	43.2

Source: Field survey (2023): Key: 0-25% = Low; 26-50% = Moderate; 51-100% = High

Table 2 show the frequency and percentage distribution of religious affiliation as a determinant of adolescent heterosexual behaviour among senior secondary school students in Rivers State. According to the findings 56% reported having engaging regularly in religious activities and indicated that their religion teaches against premarital sex, 66% of the respondents believe that premarital sex is a sin before God. However, those who reported feeling bad whenever they engage in sexual activities are just 28%. On the other hand, only 10% of the respondents reported that having a boyfriend/ girlfriend is normal for them.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between peer pressure and heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State

Table 3: Chi-square analysis on significant relationship between peer pressure and adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State

Variable			Prevalence		Test Statistics
	No	Yes	No	Yes	
Peer Pressure	No	F	190	178	$X_2(1) = 15.812$ 001
		%	15.8%	14.8%	
	Yes	F	327	505	
		%	27.3%	42.1%	

Table 3 showed chi-square analysis on the relationship between peer pressure and adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State. The study revealed a significant relationship between peer pressure and prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours ($X_2=15.812$, $df= 1$, $p<05$). Thus, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant

relationship between peer pressure and the prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State was rejected.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant relationship between religion affiliation and heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary school students in Rivers State.

Table 4: Chi-square analysis on significant relationship between religion affiliation and adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State

Variable			Prevalence		Test Statistics
	No	F	No	Yes	
Religious Affiliation	No	F	333	349	$X_2(1) = 21.255$ $P < .0001$
		%	27.8%	29.1%	
	Yes	F	184	334	
		%	15.3%	27.8%	

Table 4 showed chi-square analysis on the relationship between religious affiliation and prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State. The study revealed a significant relationship between religious affiliation and prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours ($X_2=21.255$, $df= 1$, $p<05$). Thus, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between religious affiliation and the prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State was rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The first findings show the frequency and percentage distribution of peer pressure as a determinant of adolescent heterosexual behaviour among senior secondary school students in Rivers State. According to the findings 84% reported having been encouraged by peers to engage in romantic relationships. Those who reported having been encouraged by friends to attend parties and music clubs have friends of the opposite sex and watch romantic movies and pornography by peers were 76%; while those who were encouraged by peers to engage in sexual activities were 68%. Adolescents who reported encouraged by peers to drink alcohol in order to have courage were 52%. Also, there is no significant relationship between peer pressure and the prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State was rejected. Supporting this is Forman-Alberti (2015); Dewi (2012); Widman et al. (2014) who stated that, outside of the home environment, the sexual behaviors of adolescents are greatly influenced by peers and the perceived benefits of engaging in sexual intercourse. Some adolescent believe that engaging in sexual activities increases their social status and respect among their peers, and these perceived social benefits increases their chances of adapting sexual behaviors dictated by their peers. Adolescent who associate themselves with friends who are sexually experienced and frequently communicate about sex have a higher chance of engaging in sexual norms with the intention of reaping the benefits being told by friends. This might be suggestive why most of the respondents in our study who have had sex blamed it on peer influence. This points out to the fact that friends of adolescents should never be ignored when making attempts to promote reproductive health in the community.

The second finding show the frequency and percentage distribution of religious affiliation as a determinant of adolescent heterosexual behaviour among senior secondary school students in Rivers State. According to the findings 56% reported having engaging regularly in religious activities and indicated that their religion teaches against premarital sex, 66% of the respondents believe that premarital sex is a sin before God. However, those who reported feeling bad whenever they engage in sexual activities are just 28%. On the other hand, only 10% of the respondents reported that having a boyfriend/ girlfriend is normal for them. Also, there is no significant relationship between religious affiliation and the prevalence of adolescents' heterosexual behaviours among senior secondary students in Rivers State was rejected. In agreement is Sedgh & Hussain, (2014) who stated that despite parents' knowledge on the importance of sex education, African parents see the practice as a difficult tax due to cultural beliefs and norms. Thus, the early introduction of sexual education is perceived as detrimental rather than helping the adolescent to overcome sexual and reproductive health issues.

CONCLUSION

The study reveals that a significant number of adolescents possess knowledge about reproductive health, yet they still participate in risky sexual behaviors, including kissing and sexual intercourse. This phenomenon may be attributed to various influencing factors, such as peer pressure and the pervasive impact of religious affiliation. The findings emphasize the critical need for increased awareness and the implementation of community-based initiatives to address sexual health issues affecting adolescents. Furthermore, the study highlights the importance of engaging the community in efforts to combat these challenges effectively.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were drawn:

1. Parents and school teachers should be empowered through capacity building on sexuality education so that they can teach/educate the children/students on sexual and reproductive health. This will prevent adolescents from seeking such information from their peers.
2. Religious/faith-based organizations should use their positions as a leverage to encourage adolescents to abstain from premarital sex.

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